

Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life Management, Samples and Laboratory Team

Tree of Life, Wellcome Sanger Institute, Hinxton, Cambridgeshire CB10 1SA, UK

Wellcome Sanger Institute Tree of Life Management, Samples and Laboratory Team				
Tree of Life Academic Leadership				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Head of Programme: Mark Blaxter	mb35@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-2861-949X	07/19	
Mara Lawniczak	mara@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-3006-2080	07/19	
Joana Meier	jm66@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0001-7726-2875	07/22	
Kamil S. Jaron	kj11@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-1470-5450	10/22	
Matthew Berriman			07/19	07/23
Associate Faculty				
Richard Durbin, University of Cambridge	rd@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-9130-1006	07/19	
Emma Teeling, University College, Dublin			07/19	
Honorary Faculty				
Gene Myers, Dresden Genome Center			09/19	
Associate Director Delivery and Operations				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Associate Director: Ed Symons	es13@sanger.ac.uk		06/21	11/24
Head of Production Genomics, Informatics and Core Lab				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Kerstin Howe	kj2@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-2237-513X	07/19	
Head of Project Management and Operations				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Manuel Batista	md37@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-4936-0360	09/21	

Tree of Life Laboratory				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Lead: Caroline Howard	ch25@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-1739-6569	04/20	
Aarushi Vaidya	av12@sanger.ac.uk		04/22	07/22
Abitha Thomas	at27@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-5414-9084	09/21	
Adam Bates	ab62@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0007-9129-2043	06/22	12/24
Amy Denton	ad46@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0002-9279-7899	04/22	
Benjamin Jackson	bj7@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0003-9129-4568	06/22	
David Rowland	dr16@sanger.ac.uk		05/22	02/23
Graeme Oatley	go3@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-0896-9994	08/20	
Haddijatou Mbye	hm13@sanger.ac.uk		07/19	12/22
Halyna Yatsenko	hy2@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-0917-6171	11/22	
Isabelle Clayton-Lucey	ic7@sanger.ac.uk		09/21	02/25
Juan Pablo Narváez Gomez	jn12@sanger.ac.uk		09/21	02/24
Liam Prestwood	lp15@sanger.ac.uk		07/19	08/22
Raquel Juliana Vionette do Amaral	rv5@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-0244-1745	11/20	
Priyanka Sethu Raman	pr15@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-4139-2920	10/22	
Jessie Jay	jj14@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0009-0367-8187	05/23	01/25
Elizabeth Sinclair	es25@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0004-3133-537X	09/23	
Anna Kovalevskaia	ak42@sanger.ac.uk		05/24	
Jemma Salmon	js57@sanger.ac.uk		10/24	
Charlotte Ho	ch37@sanger.ac.uk		03/25	

Project Management and Operations

name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Lead: Manuel Batista	md37@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-4936-0360	09/21	
Cam Muyo	cm38@sanger.ac.uk		06/22	
Charlie Hathaway	ch20@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-5581-0436	01/22	
Chloe Leech	cl22@sanger.ac.uk		07/19	05/23
Haoyu Niu	hn7@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-7119-3220	05/21	
Jess Bernard	jb51@sanger.ac.uk		07/19	05/24
Leah Bacon	lb33@sanger.ac.uk		05/21	05/23
Lora Downes	ld24@sanger.ac.uk			
Luke Lythgoe	ll16@sanger.ac.uk		06/21	05/24
Molly Carter	mc@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0003-9459-5593	09/21	
Rebecca O'Brien	ro8@sanger.ac.uk			
Stephanie Fagan	sf23@sanger.ac.uk	-	03/22	09/22
Theodora Anderson	ta15@sanger.ac.uk	-	09/21	01/23
Victoria McKenna	vw6@sanger.ac.uk		06/20	

Tree of Life Samples Management				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Lead: Nancy Holroyd	neh@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-2608-7151	04/20	
Radka Platte	rp3@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-0324-7562	07/19	
Ian Still	ips@sanger.ac.uk		02/21	
Nicola Chapman	nc13@sanger.ac.uk		09/20	07/23
Sinead Calnan	sc47@sanger.ac.uk		07/19	
Andy Griffiths	ag30@sanger.ac.uk		07/19	02/23
Jamie Davis	jd39@sanger.ac.uk		11/23	
Blaxter Faculty group				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Charlotte Wright	cw22@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-3971-4372	10/20	
Claudia Weber	cw21@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-5910-8898	05/20	
Ellen Cameron	ec26@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-3931-4245	09/21	
Emmelien Vancaester	ev3@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-9177-8808	06/20	04/24
Erna King	ek5@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-4567-4669	07/20	
Jessica Thomas Thorpe	jt30@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-2302-2387	04/21	
Lewis Stevens	ls30@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-6075-8273	10/20	
Manuela Kieninger	mk34@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-1841-0273	07/20	
Marcela Uliano-Silva	mu2@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0001-6723-4715	11/23	
Martha Mulongo	mm63@sanger.ac.uk	0009-0009-1235-8660	1/23	
Michael Ansah	ma29@sanger.ac.uk		1/24	
Pablo Gonzalez	pg17@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-2009-1531	01/20	10/23
Richard Challis	rc28@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-3502-1122	08/19	
Sujai Kumar	sk13@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0001-5902-6641	06/20	10/23
Ore Francis	of2@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-2678-917X	11/22	
Witek Morek	wm6@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-3547-9755	10/22	
Lawniczak Faculty group				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Lead: Mara Lawniczak	mara@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-3006-2080	07/19	
Alex Makunin	am60@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-9555-5097	07/19	
Meier Faculty group				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Lead: Joana Meier	jm66@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0001-7726-2875	07/22	
Jonah Walker	jw42@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0001-7355-3130	07/22	

Arif Maulana	am75@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-1968-4575	04/23	
Jaron Faculty group				
Kamil S. Jaron	kj11@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-1470-5450	10/22	
Sam Ebdon	se11@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0002-9321-4686	03/23	
Aleksandra Bliznina	ab66@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0001-5031-8023	03/23	
Teeling Associate Faculty group				
name	email	ORCID	date joined	date left
Yan Liang	yl10@sanger.ac.uk	0000-0003-2365-1239	10/23	